

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 4. Figure 4.25 and Figure SPM. 3b

Version: 1

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Description

The Figure 4.25 was derived from analyses implemented within the *invacost* package (Leroy et al. 2022 *Methods Ecol Evol*).

Process overview

We used the *Modelling approach* provided and explained in the *invacost* package available here <https://github.com/Farewe/invacost>. This approach consists in estimating the long-term trend in annual cost values with a statistical modelling approach. Because it includes the dynamic nature of cost values, it is probably the most robust approach to estimate average annual costs. Note that this modelling approach is not designed for extrapolations because there is no certainty that the underlying factors of costs will have similar trends in the future.

Protocol

Below, we describe the R codes used to generate the Figure 4.25 :

```
# 1/ Install the invacost package
```

```
install.packages("invacost")
```

```
library(invacost)
```

```
data(invacost)
```

```
# 2/ Selecting the database version considered in the report
```

```
invacost<- getInvaCostVersion("4.0")
```

```
# 3/ Filter the database to keep the most relevant (i.e. high and observed) data)
```

```
invacost <- invacost[which(invacost$Method_reliability == "High"), ]
```

```

invacost <- invacost[which(invacost$Implementation == "Observed"), ]
invacost <- invacost[-which(is.na(invacost$Probable_starting_year_adjusted)), ]
invacost <- invacost[-which(is.na(invacost$Probable_ending_year_adjusted)), ]

# 4/ Expand the resulting dataset to obtain the final dataset that is used in the report
db.over.time <- expandYearlyCosts(invacost,
                                startcolumn = "Probable_starting_year_adjusted",
                                endcolumn = "Probable_ending_year_adjusted")
write.csv2(db.over.time, "IPBES_Dataset.csv")

# 5/ Estimate the threshold year for which data completeness > 75%
db.over.time$Publication_lag <- db.over.time$Publication_year - db.over.time$Impact_year
quantiles <- quantile(db.over.time$Publication_lag, probs = c(.25, .5, .75))
quantiles

# 6/ Plot the global trend with the robust quadratic method
global.trend <- modelCosts(
  db.over.time, # The EXPANDED database
  minimum.year = 1970,
  maximum.year = 2019,
  incomplete.year.threshold = 2013)

p1 <- plot(global.trend,
           models = c("ols.quadratic"),
           graphical.parameters = "manual")
p2 <- p1 +
  xlab("Year") +
  ylab("Average annual cost of invasions in US$ millions") +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = c(seq(1960, 2010, by = 10), 2019)) + # X axis breaks
  theme_bw() + # Minimal theme
  scale_y_log10(breaks = 10^(-15:15), # y axis in log 10 with pretty labels
               labels = scales::comma) +
  annotation_logticks(sides = "l") + # log10 tick marks on y axis
  theme(legend.position='none')

```

p2